

Impact Damage Characterization of Aramid Aluminum Laminates

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ABSTRACT

Indentation tests were performed to model the contact behavior between aramid aluminum laminates (ARALL) and a steel ball. Subsequently, low velocity impact testing was conducted to determine the failure modes due to impact. A sectioning technique was used to examine impact damage in the laminate. The results show that the strength degradation in ARALL laminates resulting from impact depends on the fiber orientation. Strength in the transverse direction remains insensitive to impact damage, while in the fiber direction, strength decreases as impact velocity increases beyond a certain range. Residual strength after impact can be determined solely from the permanent local indentation left by the impactor.

KEYWORDS: ARALL laminates, impact damage, static indentation, contact law, fiber orientation, residual strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Impact involves the contact of two bodies, the impactor and the target. Contact force develops as the impactor indents the target. The dynamic contact sets off motion and induces damage in the target. Polymeric matrix composite laminates are known for their susceptibility to low velocity impact damage. Moreover, damage in the laminate often lies in the interior and cannot be detected easily. The inability to visually detect impact damage is an important safety issue.

Aramid aluminum laminates, ARALL laminates [1-10], offer many advantages such as light weight, high strength, and excellent fatigue properties. Moreover, they retain the advantages of aluminum, namely lower cost, easy machining, forming, and mechanical fastening abilities, as well as substantial ductility. The ARALL 2 laminates considered in this study is a 3/2 configuration consisting of three layers of high strength 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheets bonded by two layers of 3M AF-163-2U epoxy adhesive impregnated with strong unidirectional aramid fibers as shown in Figure 1. The presence of aluminum alloy sheets provides desirable ductility to the laminate. In the event of impact, the plasticity in aluminum makes it possible to generate a permanent indentation that is visible for inspection.

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In this paper, static contact behavior, impact damage characterization, and residual tensile strength of ARALL 2 laminates after impact were investigated. Due to the presence of these unidirectional fibers, material properties are expected to differ for specimens with different fiber orientations. Tests were performed on specimens in which fibers from the composite layers were parallel to the longitudinal axis of the specimen (hereafter referred to as the 0° specimens), and on specimens where the fibers were oriented 90° from the longitudinal axis (the 90° specimens). In the study of residual strength after impact, it was found that the residual strength can be correlated to the permanent indentation produced by impact.

2. CONTACT LAW

The contact law relates the force of contact to the indentation produced by pushing the indenter into the composites. The contact law is needed in the analysis of dynamic impact response of the target [11, 12]. In this study, the contact law used for loading was

$$F = k\alpha^n \quad (1)$$

where F is the contact force, k is the contact rigidity, α is the indentation depth, and n is a power index. Note that indentation α is defined as the relative displacement of the indenter and the bottom face of the specimen. To account for the permanent deformation, the equation

$$F = F_m (\alpha - \alpha_o)^q / (\alpha_m - \alpha_o)^q \quad (2)$$

proposed by Crook [13] was used to model the unloading path. In Equation (2), F_m is the contact force at which unloading begins, α_m is the indentation corresponding to F_m , and α_o denotes depth of the permanent indentation in an unloading cycle. The values of n and q are the power indices that best fit the experimental results. Equation (2) can be rewritten in the form

$$F = S (\alpha - \alpha_o)^q \quad (3)$$

in which

$$S = F_m / (\alpha_m - \alpha_o)^q \quad (4)$$

where S is an unloading rigidity. The unloading model is complete if q and α_o are determined. In this study, we further assumed that

$$\alpha_o = \begin{cases} S_p (\alpha_m - \alpha_p) & \alpha_m > \alpha_p \\ 0 & \alpha_m \leq \alpha_p \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where constants S_p and α_p are determined experimentally. In Equation (5), α_p can be considered a critical value of indentation depth beyond which permanent deformation will occur. The experimental set-up used to determine k , q , S_p , and α_p is shown in Figure 2. The specimen was 1-inch (25.4 cm) wide, and the span between clamps was 0.75-inch (19.05 cm). Each specimen was loaded with an indenter having a 0.5-inch (12.7 cm) diameter steel cap. In order to measure the

movement of the specimen with respect to the steel indenter, a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT), a device which produces an electrical output proportional to the displacement of a plunger in its core, was used. This LVDT was fixed to the loading shaft with a "c" bracket, so that the relative movement of the specimen and the indenter could be recorded. The load was measured using a load cell and a digital strain indicator. The outputs of the voltage meter from the LVDT and the strain indicator were fed into an X-Y plotter, and a continuous force-indentation curve was obtained.

To obtain data for the unloading law, the same procedure was used. However, instead of loading the specimen continuously, it was loaded and unloaded in three stages with each successive stage loaded higher than the previous one. Several tests were performed on each type of specimen to account for material variations within the specimen. Three loading tests were performed on the 0° specimens and four loading tests were performed on the 90° specimens. For unloading, three cyclic tests were performed on each specimen type. The experimental force-indentation curves obtained from the X-Y plotter were digitized using a bit-pad, and the data were used to fit loading and unloading equations. For the unloading curves, a power index q was found to be 2.5. The permanent indentation depth α_o was read directly from the digitized experimental force-indentation plots, as were the values of F_m and α_m . Figure 3 presents the typical loading curves obtained for the 0° specimens and 90° specimens. For each loading curve, the power index $n = 1.5$ was found to fit Equation (1) to the data. The experimental curves were first digitized into discrete data points and then fitted into Equation (1) using least-squares method. The contact rigidity k for each of the tests performed is listed in Table 1. The contact rigidities of the 0° and 90° specimens are similar.

Figure 4 shows typical unloading curves for the 0° specimen. From these curves we obtained the permanent indentation depth α_o corresponding to an α_m from which the unloading began. It was also found that the power index $q = 2.5$ fit Equation (3) to the unloading curves very well as shown in the solid lines in Figure 4. For unloading from an arbitrary value of α_m , the corresponding permanent indentation α_o is to be calculated from Equation (5). To determine the coefficients S_p and α_p in Equation (5), the data for α_o were plotted versus α_m for all specimens (0° and 90° specimens) as shown in Figure 5. The relation between α_o and α_m appears to be linear. A linear least-squares fit gave the following values of S_p and α_p in Equation (5).

$$S_p = 0.78 \quad , \quad \alpha_p = 5.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ inch (0.013 mm)} \quad (6)$$

3. IMPACT DAMAGE

Both 0° and 90° specimens were impacted at various velocities ranging from 30 to 65 m/s with a 0.5-inch (12.7 mm) diameter steel ball shot from a compressed air gun. Both ends of the specimen were clamped on a test stand with a span of 4 inches (101.6 mm). The impact-inflicted damage can be put in two categories, i.e., visible damage and internal damage. The former is in the form of local indentation produced by the direct contact of the projectile and the specimen. Internal damage, such as cracks in the aluminum layer and delamination or fiber breakage in the composite layer, can be observed by sectioning the specimen or using nondestructive testing techniques. To quantify the local indentation depth, the specimens were cut longitudinally through the center of the impact site after impact. Photographs were taken from the edge of each specimen through the

impact center at 2x. Tangents were drawn to the undeformed portions of the specimen, and the local indentation depth δ was measured from the intersection of these tangents to the point of maximum deformation, as shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 presents local indentation depth versus impact velocity. It is interesting to note that a linear relation exists between these two variables. For the same impact velocity, the local indentation in the 0° specimen is larger than that in the 90° specimen. This can be explained by the fact that under the same impact condition, the resulting impact force is larger in the 0° specimen. If residual strength is related to impact velocity, then it can also be related to local indentation. Thus, local indentation may be used to gauge residual strength after impact. To observe internal damage modes, the impacted specimen was sectioned longitudinally along the center line of the specimen. The cut section was polished and micrographed at 25x. This was done for impact velocities of 31, 36, 50, and 65 m/s for the 0° specimen and for 30, 37, 50, and 63 m/s for the 90° specimen.

Figures 8 and 9 show the micrographs for the 0° specimens impacted at 36 and 50 m/s, respectively. At 36 m/s, no visible damage was observed. At 50 m/s, delamination and fiber breakage in the composite layers were obvious. Also note that two of the aluminum layers were cracked near the impact point. As seen from Figure 9, the top aluminum layers fractured in the same manner as it would under tension. The fracture surface in the middle aluminum layer was inclined at approximately 45° indicating influence of transverse shear stress. At 65 m/s, all three aluminum layers were fractured along the transverse direction. The crack extended from the impact point almost to the longitudinal edges of the specimen. Figures 10 and 11 show the longitudinal sections of the 90° specimens impacted at 30 and 63 m/s, respectively. All the 90° specimens displayed inclined matrix cracks in the composite layers. The density and extent of the matrix cracks as well as delamination increase as impact velocity increases. However, even after 63 m/s impact, none of the aluminum layers cracked.

4. RESIDUAL TENSILE STRENGTH

The loss of strength of ARALL laminates after impact is of interest to the structural engineer. Due to pronounced permanent deformation of the specimen after impact, compression tests are difficult to perform without global buckling failure. For this reason, residual tensile tests were performed. All specimens were 6-inch (152.4 mm) long and 1-inch (25.4 mm) wide. The specimen was clamped at both ends leaving a 4-inch (101.6 mm) span. These specimens were impacted with a 0.5-inch (12.7 mm) diameter steel ball. The impact velocities ranged from approximately 20 to 70 m/s. Figure 12 presents the resulting residual tensile strengths versus impact velocity for both the 0° and 90° specimens. The 0° specimens show a steady decline in residual tensile strength beginning at an impact velocity of between 20 and 30 m/s. This is the range of velocity at which the laminate begins to experience fiber breakage and cracking in the aluminum layers. The 90° specimens show very little decrease in residual tensile strength until velocities exceed 60 m/s, and even then the strength reduction is small. This is consistent with our micrographic observation that the load-bearing aluminum layers in the 90° specimen do not fracture up to this impact velocity.

Using the relation between impact velocity and local indentation δ established earlier shown in Figure 7, the residual strength plot of Figure 12 was replotted in terms of residual strength versus δ as shown in Figure 13. It is evident that local indentation correlates with residual strength very

well. This relation can provide a convenient way to establish residual strength by measuring local indentation after impact. To investigate whether local indentations produced statically would have the same effect on laminate strength, additional static indentation tests were performed. The specimen was clamped as in the impact test. Local indentations were measured in a manner similar to that performed after the impact tests. The specimens used for the static indentation tests were subsequently subjected to tension tests to determine their residual strengths. Figure 14 presents the residual tensile strength versus local indentation from specimens subjected to the static indentation test. Comparing this result with that in Figure 13, we note the similarity despite more scatter in the static data. However, beyond 70 m/s impact velocity, the residual strength of the 0° specimen seems to drop drastically. This behavior is somewhat different from the static case as shown in Figure 14. Nevertheless, for impact velocities below 70 m/s, the residual strength of the ARALL laminates may be predicted from the depth of the local indentation whether it is produced by static or impact loading.

5. CONCLUSIONS

From this study, it was found that the strength degradation in ARALL 2 laminates resulting from impact depends on fiber orientation. In the transverse direction, strength is insensitive to impact damage, while in the fiber direction, strength decreases as impact velocity increases beyond a certain range.

An interesting finding is that the residual strength after impact can be determined solely from the local indentation produced by the impact. Moreover, this residual strength-local indentation relation can be established using static indentation tests. This interesting characteristic of the ARALL laminates makes it feasible to employ visual inspection of the local indentation caused by impact to estimate the residual strength of an impacted structure.

Further research is needed in translating the effect of this local damage to the real structure. For example, if an equivalent elliptical hole is used to represent the local damage inflicted by impact, then the local indentation should be related to the size of the elliptical hole.

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Table 1
Experimental Loading Data

Fiber Orientation of Specimen	Test No.	k	Ave. k	n
0°	1	3.15x10 ⁶	2.37x10 ⁶	1.5
	2	2.17x10 ⁶		1.5
	3	1.79x10 ⁶		1.5
90°	1	1.16x10 ⁶	1.70x10 ⁶	1.5
	2	1.24x10 ⁶		1.5
	3	2.16x10 ⁶		1.5
	4	2.26x10 ⁶		1.5

ARALL 2 Laminates Standard 3/2 Layup
Figure 1

Schematic Diagram for the Indentation Set-Up
Figure 2

Least-Squares Fit for Loading Curves of
0° and 90° Specimens Using $n = 1.5$
Figure 3

Least-Squares Fit for Unloading Curves
of 0° Specimen Using $q = 2.5$
Figure 4

Relation between Permanent Indentation
and Maximum Indentation
Figure 5

Method of Measuring Local Deflection
Figure 6

Local Indentation as a Function of Impact Velocity for 0° and 90° Specimens
Figure 7

Micrograph of Longitudinal Cross-Section through Impact Center (25x) of 0° Specimen Impacted at 36 m/s
Figure 8

Micrograph of Longitudinal Cross-Section through Impact Center (25x) of 0° Specimen Impacted at 50 m/s
Figure 9

Micrograph of Longitudinal Cross-Section through Impact Center (25x) of 90° Specimen Impacted at 30 m/s
Figure 10

Micrograph of Longitudinal Cross-Section through Impact Center (25x) of 90° Specimen Impacted at 63 m/s
Figure 11

Residual Tensile Strength as a Function of Impact Velocity for 0° and 90° Specimens
Figure 12

Residual Tensile Strength as a Function of Local Indentation for 0° and 90° Specimens
Figure 13

Residual Tensile Strength versus Local Indentation for Static Loading
Figure 14